

An error has been made inadvertently in the conflict of interest declaration of the article titled "The mythological connections of the four sacred elements and four directions in the old Turkish belief system: The miracle motives in Velâyetnames four-doors forty stations. *Art and Interpretation*, 44, 68-78. 10.47571/sanatyorum.1509587" published in the 2024 issue 44 of the Sanat ve Yorum Dergisi, and it needs to be updated as follows.

Conflict of Interest: "The author of this article is also the editor-in-chief of this journal. This situation is considered to be a relationship that may create a conflict of interest. In order to ensure an impartial and transparent refereeing process, the refereeing and publication decision regarding this article was carried out by the guest editor assigned to the journal. The guest editor was appointed by the Atatürk University Coordinatorship of Scientific Journals Office. Blind refereeing was applied during the evaluation of the article and the author's editorial position was not disclosed to the referees. In addition, all stages of this process were managed in accordance with the journal's ethical rules and international ethical guidelines such as COPE and ICMJE in order to prevent conflicts of interest."